
The Relationship between Quality Measurement and Efficiency Improvement in Health Care Systems

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Abstract

Quality measurement in health care organisation is most often considered as measures for cost-saving and error reduction in the clinical procedures. The concept of quality measurement in health care organisations is the analysis of effectiveness and accuracy in procedures for patients' diagnosis and treatment. This study aimed to find the relationship between quality measurement and efficiency improvements in the healthcare sector of Mauritius. This was executed by using mixed methodological approach. The blending of qualitative and quantitative methodologies assisted in analysing perceptions of healthcare professionals and service users. The sample population for this research consisted of 1800 individuals for quantitative phase, whereas, 10 participants were considered for qualitative phase of this research. The research outcomes declared the presence of a positive relationship between quality measures and efficiency improvement in the healthcare sector. The key research findings are (i) the presence of a positive relationship between quality measures and efficiency improvement in the healthcare sector; (ii) that efficiency improvement in healthcare organisation can be achieved by standardisation of the organisational procedures, and improving the efficacy of employees associated with healthcare organisation and (iii) that improvement in information technology also contributes improving efficiency levels of healthcare organisations.

Keywords: *Quality measurement, efficiency improvement, Mauritius health care sector, health care systems, mixed methods.*

1. Introduction

The concept of quality in healthcare organisations is considered in terms of reduction in mortality rates and

satisfactory clinical improvement among patients. Wiig *et al.* [1] stated that quality measures within the healthcare organisation might also be considered in terms of cost-saving and error reduction in the clinical procedures taking place in healthcare organisations. The concept of quality measurement in health care organisations can also be considered by analysing the effectiveness and accuracy in procedures for patients' diagnosis and treatment. Similarly, quality of care might also be considered by analysing the degree to which the healthcare professionals have been following best medical practices for facilitating patients [1]. The quality measure might also be considered in terms of outcomes measures of patients. The processes of quality and efficiency improvement assist healthcare organisations in facilitating service users in the best possible manner. The research conducted by Ogrinc *et al.* [2] stated that efficiency improvement processes in healthcare organisation need to involve processes related to supply, demands, quality of processes, impacts of services and patients' outcomes. For this reason, the processes and strategies of efficiency improvement are also influenced by a variety of factors [2].

Organisations tend to improve quality of their services by introducing new technologies in healthcare systems and increasing healthcare facilities for their service users. The research conducted by Obermeyer *et al.* [3] stated that quality measurement is performed by analysing the principles implemented in the healthcare system. The quality measurement is also dependent on the ability of an organisation to plan, organise, direct, control, coordinate, and evaluate resources and procedures of healthcare services. Similarly, the research conducted by Armony *et al.* [4] demonstrated that the voluminous of the additional human and material resources contribute to efficiency improvement within the healthcare organisations. The involvement of healthcare professionals in the establishment and implementation of care related regulations and protocols

has also been found to improve the efficiency of healthcare services.

The healthcare sector of Mauritius can be considered amongst less developed healthcare systems across the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO) has ranked Mauritius on 84th rank, with respect to quality of health services [5]. The healthcare system of Mauritius has been facing ambiguities due to lack of resources and funds. The concerned authorities of this region have been focusing on improving primary healthcare setup of this region, for facilitating service users [5]. The use of innovations and technology has also been assisting in improving the quality of services delivered from the platform of healthcare sector of Mauritius. The healthcare sector of Mauritius has been implementing quality measurement and quality management processes, for improving the overall efficiency of healthcare services [5].

The purpose of this research is to analyse processes of quality measurement and efficiency improvement in healthcare organisations. This research also aims to analyse the relationship between quality measurement and efficiency improvement in healthcare sector of Mauritius. This research further aims to analyse, explore, identify, and describe the perceptions of today's health care executives, administration executives, and health administration program managers about processes of quality measurement and efficiency improvement.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Measurement of Quality in the Healthcare Sector

The healthcare organisations provide facilities to the service users, such that low-quality care services can result in severe medical complications. For this reason, quality is considered as the matter of survival in health care administration. Employees associated with the higher managerial level of the healthcare organisation are responsible for the delivery of high-quality services to users. The quality measurement process within the healthcare organisation is cyclic in nature. Various departments work in collaboration with each other for the provision of quality care services to users. The process of quality measurement is initiated from the production chain and needs to be maintained throughout till the delivery of care service.

The research conducted by McPherson and Pincus [6] stated that the concept of quality measurement has acquired a lot of attention among organisations of different sectors. The service users of healthcare organisations are most often extremely demanding; however, their demands are entirely based on the nature of their required care service. With the increment in technology levels and the competitiveness, the level of quality in healthcare services have been significantly

increasing. The healthcare organisations have been utilising quality measurement and quality control programs which gave rise to the advent of ISO certification programs. These ISO and other standardisation programs have also led towards the advent of other parameters for improving organisational performance [7].

The technological advancement within the healthcare sector has changed work processes up to certain extent, causing a significant increment in the quality of services. The evolution of healthcare management within the health care organisations and delivery of medical services on a large scale have changed the measures which were previously utilised for the measuring quality of services delivered through the platform of healthcare organisations [8].

The use of technology within the healthcare sector has previously assisted in mass production, increasing the necessity of strict inspection of products. In this regard, the use of technology in the healthcare sector has raised the need of quality inspection within the healthcare sector. Khanassov *et al.* [9], stated that the development of quality control department within the healthcare organisation is anticipated to have a significant influence on total quality measurement and control within the healthcare organisation.

Yang *et al.* [8] stated that organisations are responsible to utilise the available resources in the best possible manner for improving their business. Organisations belonging to the health sector also carry out businesses; however, the foremost objective of healthcare organisations is to improve health and well-being of service users. The healthcare organisations also utilise different managerial approaches for analysing current quality standards implemented within the organisations. For instance, the approach of Strategic Quality Management involves different phases which initially analyse the currently implemented policies and procedures within the healthcare organisation. The strategic quality management includes the use of behavioural techniques for dealing with external and internal clients and the formation of teams consisting of skilled individuals for carrying out routine procedures in an effective manner.

2.2 Quality Management in Healthcare

Quality management is referred to as general ways of managing organisations. The focus of quality management is continuous improvement in the healthcare sector, with the intention of providing high quality patient care and satisfying employees. The acts of measuring and managing quality is defined as the process of seeking assurance from service users about the levels of expertise of healthcare professionals. Similar to quality measurement, the process of quality

management is also considered as one of the most important factor assuring the provision of high quality services to the service users [10]. It is crucial for an organisation to implement quality management processes within the organisations. Moreover, the involvement of top management is essential for carrying out quality management in effective manner.

Similar to the management of organisations of other sectors, the management of healthcare sector is also responsible to organise itself to reduce losses and to provide high quality care at affordable cost. The provision of facilities to service users is also an integral part of the quality management process. Expenditures within the healthcare organisation have boosted the development of new positions within the management; therefore, the healthcare organisations need to be considered as business entities. Similar to the organisations of other sector, the healthcare organisations also implement various tools and carry out a variety of procedures for managing the quality of care services delivered through their platform.

The research conducted by Sultan [10] analysed the impact of cloud computing and ISO standards on quality management within the healthcare organisations. He responded that the use of cloud computing and ISO standards might not always enough to improve the quality of healthcare services. In this regard, it is imperative for the organisational management to analyse the specificities of health quality, the organisational culture, and the characteristics of other organisational procedures from the context of ISO standards [10]. This research was focused towards the healthcare sector in Mauritius; therefore, when the private sector healthcare organisations of Mauritius were analysed, it was found that they have been upgrading their procedures with reference to the ISO standards.

Implementation of quality management system within the healthcare organisation by using ISO standards is the extremely complex process. The research conducted by Wright *et al.* [11] stated that individuals working in the healthcare organisations might experience complications due to professional bureaucracy within the organisation. On the other hand, the research conducted by Davis *et al.* [12] stated that the implementation of quality measurement and quality management processes within the healthcare organisation might be failed due to lacking in depth of organisational analysis. For this reason, prior to the introduction of quality measurement and quality management programs, it is essential to consider organisational culture, and the organisational objectives prior to the implementation of processes of quality improvement. The failures of implementing quality measurements and quality improvement programs within the healthcare organisations are not only resulted

due to poor implementation of organisational skills; rather is also resulted due to the dissatisfaction of clients. The conceptualisation of quality services is not easier to implement within the healthcare organisations. For this reason, it is essential to consider holistic aspect of caring for during the implementation of quality standards. In this regard, the quality measurement and quality management programs are required to be initiated by combined efforts of health care professionals and other managerial staff working in the healthcare organisation. The research conducted by Armony *et al.* [13] stated that being health care professionals, nurses usually spend more time in caring for patients. For this reason, there is need to consider the attitude of nurses towards quality of services, the requirement of monitoring of services, and the anticipated impact of the involvement of healthcare professionals in the quality management process.

Weller *et al.* [14] emphasised that commonly utilised quality management model can be considered to impact the organisational decision-making ability in systematic and rational manner. Yang *et al.* [8] stated that quality measurement and management demonstrate the the elements of the organisation's identity. The process of quality measurement can also be considered as a style of management, hierarchies, guidelines, mission and vision. Quality measurement within the healthcare organisation is intended to improve the efficiency of healthcare services. Quality measurement processes also assist in enhancing satisfaction levels of service users. The Quality measurement and quality improvement processes consists of the ISO standards. . Figure 1 demonstrate the components of ISO standards for healthcare organisations.

Figure 1: ISO Standards in Health Care Organisations (Source: Gilbert, 2017)

2.3 Efficiency Improvement in Healthcare Sector

For this reason, the processes of efficiency improvement are dependent on a range of factors. For instance, the research conducted by Khanassov *et al.* [9] demonstrated that quality and efficiency improvement in healthcare organisations include the combination of technical, scientific, material, and human characteristics. Efficiency improvement also consists of the efficiency levels of workforce associated with the healthcare organisation. The quality of services delivered through the platform of healthcare organisations is also dependent on the expectations of service users. For instance, service users admitted in private healthcare sector normally tend to possess high levels of expectations, as compared to other patients [9]. The healthcare organisations need to improve the quality of their services within a restrained budget; therefore, hospital management might fail to improve the efficiency of their services by considering inadequate budget. Likewise, efficiency improvement is also dependent on the expertise levels of healthcare professionals employed in health care organisation. The healthcare organisations are responsible for arranging training opportunities for their employees; however, lacking in the provision of training opportunities is anticipated to have a reduced efficiency of healthcare services.

On the contrary, the research conducted by Goetsch *et al.* [15] demonstrated efficiency in terms of the use of information and resources for making important decisions. Efficiency was also discussed in terms of the provision of better quality service, by considering minimum cost. Similarly, the research conducted by Ogrinc *et al.* [2] stated that efficiency improvement processes in healthcare organisation need to involve processes related to supply, demands, quality of processes, impacts of services and patients' outcomes.

3. Ethical Clearance

This study was conducted after acquiring ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board.

4. Research Methodology

The researcher considered the mixed methodological approach. The pragmatic paradigm assisted in conducting in-depth analysis by collecting data by using survey questionnaire and interview analysis. The triangulation of qualitative and quantitative methodology is anticipated to contribute in performing robust data analysis. The qualitative phase of this research assisted researcher in analysing perceptions, views, and narrations of healthcare professionals and patients visiting the considered healthcare organisation. The research performed by using qualitative methodology also contribute in maintaining confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity of research

participants. On the contrary, quantitative research approach utilises analysis of numerical data by using statistical tools [16]. The quantitative methodology can be considered as the reliable mode of inquiry, as compared to qualitative research. The mixed methodological approach combine the philosophy, the research design orientation, and methods of qualitative and quantitative research techniques, which might assist in acquiring reliable and robust research outcomes [17].

4.1. Hypotheses

The researcher considered following hypotheses.

H1: There is no difference between the workforce efficiency and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H2: There is no difference between the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

5. Research Setting

This research was performed by considering some healthcare organisations situated in the Republic of Mauritius. At the end of year 2015, there were 2,550 physicians registered to the Medical Council of the Republic of Mauritius, such that there were 20.2 physicians per 10,000 populations [18]. This research included healthcare organisations consisting of at least 100 beds. Some of the healthcare organisations were selected for this research based on ease of accessibility. AG Jeetoo Hospital, Apollo Bramwell, Victoria in Quatres Borne, and Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam National Hospital were included in this research.

6. Population and Sampling

The healthcare executives, search firm executives, board members, and health administration managers were asked to provide their responses. Moreover, the healthcare professionals were also considered as research participants. The quality of health care services can also be analysed in the light of perceptions of patients and potential service users; therefore, patients visiting health care organisations were also considered as research participants.

This mixed-methodological research was completed in two phases; qualitative and quantitative phase. For this reason, two types of sample sizes were considered for this research. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for calculating sample size. The effect size at 0.10, power at 0.80, and the alpha set at 0.05 was used for analysing sample size for qualitative phase of research. Approximately 1800 respondents were included in quantitative phase of this research. On the other hand, 10 research participants were considered for qualitative phase of this research.

The research used stratified sampling for selecting research participants for the quantitative phase of this research. The stratified sampling is appropriate for dealing with large sample size because it assures the availability of subgroups within the selected sample population [19]. On the other hand, purposive sampling was considered for qualitative phase of this research. The theoretical purposive sampling include a joint collection of theory and data analysis, assisting in the generation of theory; therefore, this sampling is appropriate for exploratory qualitative research [20].

7. Data Collection Tools

Data collection for this research was performed by using close-ended questionnaire surveys and semi-structured interviews. The semi-structured interviews were performed for this research in focus. Semi-structured interview sessions was deemed the most appropriate data collection tool for collecting descriptive information. This research needs to include perceptions, and experiences of research participants; therefore, interview sessions assisted in acquiring in-depth information from the sample population [16]. The semi-structured interviews assist in acquiring perceptions of research participants about a certain phenomenon. The questionnaire for semi-structured interview was self-administered. The research participants were asked to participate in this research by providing informed consent and cover letter explaining research aims and objectives.

On the other hand, close-end questionnaire was designed for quantitative phase of this research. The respondents of quantitative phase of this research were asked to select the most appropriate option from 5 point-Likert scales, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Close-ended questionnaire survey assists researcher in leading the entire research in a particular direction.

8. Reliability of Data Collection Tool

The reliability of quantitative data collection tool was measured by using Cronbach's alpha. This statistical test was performed to measure the reliability of each statement included in the survey questionnaire.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	Percent
Cases	Valid	1750	97.2
	Excluded ^a	50	2.8
	Total	1800	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.632	67

The value of Cronbach's alpha for this research was 0.623, indicating the reliability of research questionnaire, thus presenting reliability of the questionnaire survey. The reliability index used by Bonett and Wright [21] was used in this research. Bonett and Wright [21] stated that items and dimensions of questionnaire survey can be considered as psychometrically sound at the hospital level. For this reason, the assessment the reliability index can be utilised for analysing the efficacy of health care services in health care system.

The researcher also assured the reliability of the qualitative data collection tool. The qualitative data collection tool was informed in verbatim and words quotes. The interview was conducted in the form of the focus group, such that each of the interview transcripts was recorded, coded, and thematically analysed.

9. Credibility and Transferability of Research

This research was conducted by considering only four hospitals because of having limited time and financial resources. The outcomes acquired by considering the following 4 hospitals had not limited research outcomes for the following hospitals. For this reason, research outcomes could be transferable for other healthcare organisations of Mauritius. The credibility of this research is confirmed due to the recruitment of employees belonging to various managerial levels. The names, related titles, and certifications related to healthcare administrations were affirmed prior to the inclusion of healthcare employees in research process.

10. Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted after acquiring ethical approval from the university. The confidentiality of research participants was assured to save research participants from intended harm. Moreover, the participant's reciprocity was also maintained in this research. The ethical consideration related to the use of

collected data fairly and lawfully was also assured by the research. The research performed necessary measures for to keep confidentiality and anonymity of data. The data acquired from research participants was kept safe till the completion of research and was discarded later.

10. Results and Findings

10.1 Quantitative Phase

10.1.1 Variables.

Table 2: Dependent and Independent Variables

Dependent Variable	
1.	Overall Quality of Health Care (QHC)
Independent Variable	
1.	ISO Quality Standards Compliance (ISO)
2.	Workforce Efficiency (WE)

The dependent variable for this research was overall quality of health care administration. The quality measurement and efficiency improvement of healthcare organisations are dependent on various factors. Two of these factors; ISO quality standards and workforce efficiency were considered as independent variables for this research. Variables included in this research were given initials in order to make it easy to put in statistical software.

10.1.2 Demographics.

The quantitative phase of this research included a wide number of research participants. The demographic information of the respondents include information about age, gender, and academic qualification of respondents. The perceptions and attitudes of respondents are strongly influenced by their age and experiences. Table 2 represented demographic details of the research participants.

Table 3: Demographic Statistics

Demographic Statistics				
		Age 1= 25-30 years, 2=31-40 years; 3=41-50 years)	Gender	Educational Level 1= 5 years, 2=7 years; 3=10 years)
N	Valid	1750	1750	1750
	Missing	50	50	50
Mean		2.93	2.68	1.27
Median		2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		2	2	2

Std. Deviation	5.211	1.196	10.035
Variance	10.258	1.955	5.692

Mean value for age of respondents was 2.93 for age, 2.68 for gender, and 1.27 for educational qualification. Similarly, the values of standard deviations for age, gender, and educational levels were 10.21, 10.19, and 10.03 respectively.

10.1.3 QHC in comparison WE

H₁: There is no difference between the workforce efficiency and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 4: Paired Sample Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QHC WE	3.00	1750	0.43	.011
	3.00	1750	0.35	.009

Table 4 mentioned pair sample statistics for QHC and WE. The mean value for the QHC and WE was 3.00 each (n=1750). On the other hand, the standard deviation for the QHC and WE was 0.43 and 0.35.

Table 5: Paired Sample Test

	Paired Differences				Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		
			Lower	Upper	
QHC WE	-0.01	0.55	-0.03	-0.02	0.05

The outcomes of pair sampled statistics declared the presence of statistically significant difference between QHC and WE. Analysing the statistical outcomes, it could be stated that the research participants demonstrating preference for workforce efficiency principally experienced better quality of care.

10.1.4 QHC in comparison ISO

H₂: There is no difference between the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 6: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QHC ISO	3.00	1750	0.43	0.01
	3.01	1750	0.45	0.01

Table 6 represented the mean for the QHC for (n=1800) was 3.00, whereas, mean for the ISO standards was 3.01. The standard deviation values for for the QHC and ISO were 0.43 and 0.45.

Table 7: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences				Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		
			Lower	Upper	
QHC ISO	-0.01	0.63	-0.04	0.24	0.02

The paired sample statistics declared the presence of statistical significance between QHC and ISO. Mean for ISO compliance was less than the mean value for quality of healthcare; therefore, it can be concluded that the research participants who represented preference for ISO standards had experience better quality of care.

10.2 Qualitative Phase

The responses acquired from research participants were thematically analysed. Rubin and Babbie [22] stated that the use of thematic analysis in qualitative research assist in determining links between research objectives and research findings. The research participants were asked to provide their responses about the factors representing efficiency improvement within the healthcare organisation. The research participants employed at different management levels stated that efficiency of an organisation can be analysed in terms of the use of information technology.

The responses of directors, managers, health care employees and other leaders in health administration stated that " *the innovative use of health care technology would be different in different place and different situation. It does not have any standard definition. Different country has different infrastructure according to their economic condition, manpower and geographical structure. If anybody uses ISO for medical care whether it is store-forward or real time; in that sense we are doing telemedicine in Mauritius.* "

The healthcare professionals responded that when the healthcare organisation lack technological advancement, it might give rise to various types of errors. The research participants were asked about factors which increase the risk of errors in healthcare organisations. The IT Executive responded, " *There is requirement to upgrade system and information – accurate delivery of information are the most significant factors. Sometimes*

a lack of understanding and training cause errors. In case of HR – there is requirement to develop systems to deliver accurate information.”

Measurement of quality of healthcare services in Mauritius can be analysed by considering the implementation of information technology within the healthcare sector of Mauritius. Some of the healthcare organisations lack facilities related to the laboratory diagnostic tests. The research participants were interrogated about the potential impact of lack of innovations and technological advancement in healthcare sector of Mauritius. One of the respondent declared, *“it is not so good for our country as well as the patients. The country is losing money and patients have to go far to achieve quality health service and pay more; where as we have all of elements to ensure these facilities.”*

The lack of availability of resources have a significant impact on the satisfaction levels so service users. The service measure quality of healthcare sector in terms of availability of diagnostic tests for them. One of the respondents demonstrated; *“when a patient came here for follow-up his cardiac operation was done in last year, patient became very pleased by the response of consultant. It is because of database; health care professionals are maintaining their patient’s database (EHR). Whenever a patient comes for follow-up, health care professionals can have all record by EHR very easily and quickly. Patients are satisfied because health care professionals are concerned about them. Our medical specialists are enough qualified but we don’t have enough ICT culture among health personnel....there are other constrains such as high price of bandwidth and interrupted power supply.”*

11. Discussion

This research was directed to analyse the relationship between quality measurement and efficiency improvement in health care sector of Mauritius. Thus performed by considering two factors which were anticipated to impact quality measurement and efficiency improvement in health care sector. These two factors include ISO standards and workforce efficiency. The combination of qualitative and quantitative techniques made significant revelations in this research. Having considered sufficiently large and well stratified sampling, the outcomes of this research can be considered as generalised for the healthcare sector of Mauritius.

Outcomes of research participants acquired from qualitative and quantitative research demonstrated that the concept of quality management within the healthcare organisation might vary from one individual to the other. Participants were health care professionals, employees working in other sectors of healthcare, and service users.

In this regard, this research assisted in acquiring different perspective related to quality measurement in health care. The responses of healthcare professionals and service users demonstrated that quality measurement within the healthcare organisation has been usually analysed in terms of utilisation of information technology and innovations within the healthcare sector. Technological innovations are not only anticipated to improve satisfaction levels of patients; rather also increase the expertise levels of the healthcare professionals. In this regard, the use of technology can improve efficiency levels of the services delivered from the platform of health care organisation. The outcomes of this research were found to be consistent with the outcomes of research conducted by Schembri [23], who analysed the impact of information technology and monitoring of clients on quality of services delivered through the platform of health care organisation.

Research participants also provided their opinions about the quality measurement processes within the healthcare organisations. The research outcomes declared that effective administration is crucial for measuring quality in the healthcare organisations. The healthcare organisation tend to continuously improve the services delivered through their platform; however, it is also crucial to appropriately administer and train healthcare professionals. The healthcare organisation arranges on job training sessions for their employees for improving their expertise levels [24]. The workforce efficiency contributes to overall quality improvement within the healthcare organisations [25]. The responses of research participants declared that quality measurement might also be analysed in terms of the levels of communication between healthcare professionals and employees working in different departments of healthcare organisation [26]. The responses of research participants declared that the lack of communication between different departments of organisations negatively impacts the workforce efficiency. These outcomes are similar to the outcomes of research conducted by Bork-Hüffer [27].

The quality measurement of health care services can also be analysed in terms of accessibility of health care services to the general population [28]. The government of Mauritius has been improving the healthcare facilities for their residents; however, for increasing satisfaction levels of their service users, they are required to reduce the cost of healthcare services. The affordability of healthcare service for the targeted service users improves the overall efficiency of health care organisation. Outcomes acquired by analysing the responses acquired from research participants declared that there are certain factors which limit workforce efficiency. These factors include political, cultural, and financial problems within the healthcare organisations [29]. The managerial

changes within the healthcare organisations might improve efficiency of healthcare services [30]. The healthcare organisations of Mauritius are required to measure quality of healthcare services in terms of the workforce efficiency and the standardisation of currently implemented procedures within the health care organisations.

12. Conclusion

The quality measurement process can be considered as the pre-requisite of the efficiency improvement in Mauritius healthcare sector. The healthcare sector of Mauritius has been improving the quality of care services delivered through their platform. The process of quality measurement allows organisation management in identifying the factors decreasing the overall quality of services performed from their platform. The analysis of these factors assists management in limiting the impact of these factors and increasing the overall effectiveness of services delivered through that particular platform. The efficiency improvement in the healthcare sector of Mauritius is also dependent on the administration of management. Most of the healthcare organisations lack appropriate administration by qualified and experienced professionals. The healthcare organisations tend to provide integrated care to the service users; however, some of the sectors of healthcare organisations do not interact with each other, resulting in the delivery fewer quality services from the platform of health care organisation. Quality measurement in health care organisations of Mauritius can also be analysed in terms of use of technology and innovations within the healthcare sector.

The healthcare sector of Mauritius has been focusing on the hospital management by analysing factors impacting the quality of healthcare sector. The quality measurement process is essential to implement changes within the healthcare organisations. The quality measurement also lead towards efficiency improvement, resulting in the provision of better healthcare services to the service users. Efficiency improvement within the healthcare organisations is dependent on the utilisation of funds by healthcare management and the nature of training opportunities for employers working in health care organisation. In the light of perceptions acquired from the research participants, it can be concluded that quality measurement within healthcare organisations is strongly based on the performance and expertise levels of health care professionals. The improved information technology also tends to improve the overall efficiency of health care services. The health care management need to consider all of these factors for the provision of quality services to their service users. The research outcomes declared the presence of positive relationship between the quality measurement process and efficiency

improvement. The Mauritian hospitals was have been striving to take necessary measures for fulfilling the demands of service users.

The outcomes of this research can be used as implications for policy makers and healthcare providers. The quality improvement processes within the healthcare organisations are considered to assist in the delivery of quality services to the users. The delivery of quality clinical procedures also increase business of organisations. In this regard, the efficiency improvement can also contribute to attain financial incentives. Moreover, quality improvement in healthcare services is also anticipated to improve clinical outcomes of users.

13. Acknowledgment

I am thankful to God for offering me this chance to be able to complete this task. I would also like to show gratitude to my supervisor and parents for being there for me. My friends and classmates, you all are equally acknowledged for supporting me through the course of research.

14. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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